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On the left are plants grown from seeds harvested only six days after they were pollinated; on the right old weighs only 5 milligrams, instead of 35 milligrams for a normal adult grain. The small seedlings, alt

THE GERMINATION OF BARLEY SEEDS HARVESTED AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF GROWTH

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AT ABERDEEN, Idaho, where these experiments were conducted under irrigation, in cooperation with the Idaho Agricultural Experiment Station, a kernel of Hannchen barley is normally mature at 26 days after flowering. In 1920 an experiment was undertaken to determine the earliest date after pollination at which seeds were sufficiently developed to germinate. In this experiment samples from seven varieties were taken. Three

of these varieties were six-rowed and four were two-rowed. Sufficient spikes of equal development were tagged in each variety. The dates of flowering of the spikes were determined by observations and later checked by measurements of the kernels. These dates are not absolutely accurate as the flowers on a spike are not all fertilized on the same day. In all varieties the tip and basal flowers are pollinated later than those on the central part of the spike.

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...a mature seeds, with intermediate stages at intervals of one day. The dry matter in a barley seed six days ...e slender than those from mature seeds, develop normally and produce seed. (Fig. 16.)

In the six-rowed varieties the flowers of the central rows are pollinated before those of the lateral rows.

In four of the varieties the first samples were taken six days after flowering. In one variety the first sample was taken seven days, in a second, eight days, and in a third, nine days after flowering. These samples were taken by cutting the culms and placing the spikes in paper envelopes. The seeds were not taken from the spikes until the following winter when the germination was tested by sowing the seeds in flats in the greenhouse at Arlington Farm, Virginia. The seeds were placed in rows spaced at definite distances and covered lightly with soil.

When the experiment was planned in 1920 it was thought that germination would first occur in seeds which had developed for about 14 days. In mature seed the embryo is provided with an epithelial layer which secretes the diastase necessary for the digestion of the starch endosperm. The epithelial layer is not fully formed until about

the 14th day after the flower is fertilized. There are several other changes that take place at this time which indicate approaching maturity. A secondary stage of starch formation commences. The peak of the water content of the kernel is reached at this time.

It is readily seen in the table that the hypothesis of time of germination was not correct. It was thought that all samples were taken sufficiently early to show the inception and gradual increase in percentage of germination. All of the varieties showed germination at six days from flowering. The Baku variety gave a perfect percentage of germination at that age. It may be possible that the Gatami shows the progress that should be expected. On the 6th day after flowering four of the seven central kernels germinated while only three of the seven lateral ones germinated. On the 7th day all of the central kernels were viable while only six of the seven lateral ones grew. It was not until the 8th day after the spikes were recorded as flowering that

all of the lateral kernels could be germinated. The flowers of the central spikelets are pollinated first. The lateral ones usually are pollinated one or two days later.

Barley kernels six days of age are very small. They have a very high water content and when dried are so small and brittle as to be difficult to handle. In the average kernel of Hannchen barley at this stage there are only 5 milligrams of dry matter, while at maturity there are 35. The plants produced from these small kernels are very slender and the first leaves are very small. They are perfectly normal, however, and develop into normal plants which produce seed. When grown under the conditions of this

experiment the adult plants were not as robust as those from mature seed, but this may have been a result of their having been transplanted. The seedlings were progressively taller and had greater diameter of stem with the increase of the age and size of seed, as may be seen in Fig. 16.

In 1921 a more accurate study was made with Hannchen barley. Several hundred flowers were emasculated within a period of three or four hours. Two days later these were hand-pollinated and a record made of the exact time of pollination. As barley pollen either germinates or dies within a few minutes after the anther is ruptured, the ages of these kernels are known certainly within one hour. As will be seen in the

Results of experiments in germination of kernels of barley varieties harvested at different stages of development after flowering

Days from Flowering	1920																1921						
	Himalaya				Gatami				Manchuria				Hannchen		Jet		Baku		Chevalier		Hannchen		
	Central Kernels		Lateral Kernels		Central Kernels		Lateral Kernels		Central Kernels		Lateral Kernels												
	Planted	Germinated	Planted	Germinated	Planted	Germinated	Planted	Germinated	Planted	Germinated	Planted	Germinated											
2																					10	0	
3																						10	0
4																						10	0
5																						10	9
6	9	8	10	8	7	4	7	3														10	6
7	10	9	10	9	7	7	7	6	10	10	9	9										10	6
8	9	9	9	6	8	8	8	8	12	12	12	10	9	8								10	8
9	10	9	10	10	7	5	7	7	11	11	9	9	12	11								10	7
10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	13	13	13	12	11	11	4	4	5	5	10	10	10	10	2
11	10	10	10	10	8	7	8	7	8	8	8	7	13	13	6	6	7	7	12	10			
12	7	7	7	7	8	8	8	7	7	7	7	6	10	10	4	4	7	7	10	8			
13	8	8	8	8	9	9	7	7	11	11	9	9	12	12	6	6	4	4					
14	10	10	10	10	6	6	6	6	7	7	7	7	11	11	8	8	6	6					
15	9	9	9	9	7	7	7	7	10	10	9	9	13	13	7	7	7	7					
16	10	10	11	11	8	8	8	8	12	12	12	12	12	12	7	7	6	6					
17	9	9	9	9	7	7	7	7	12	12	12	12	10	10	8	8	8	8					
18	10	10	10	10	7	7	7	7	9	9	9	9	10	10	7	7	6	6					
19	9	9	8	8	8	8	8	8	13	13	11	11	10	10	8	8	8	8					
20	9	9	9	8	7	7	7	6							7	7	7	7					
21					7	7	6	6							9	9	8	8					
22															8	8	7	6					
23															8	8	8	8					
24															8	8	6	6					
25															6	6							

table, nine out of ten kernels germinated at an age of five days from the time they were pollinated. The fact that so many kernels germinated at five days and the irregularity of the later germinations indicate that an occasional seed might be found which would germinate at less than five days.

There is some question as to the effect of the kernels being allowed to

remain on the spike as was done in this experiment. The spikes dry very rapidly at Aberdeen. It is thought that no additional material enters the seed from the spike for a period longer than one hour after the culm has been severed from the plant. Further experiments are being conducted to discover more of the details of germination at early ages.

SOME POINTS ON THE RELATION OF CYTOLOGY AND GENETICS

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IT IS necessary to point out certain misstatements of fact made by Miss E. Eleanor Carothers in her review of Sharp's *Cytology* in the *JOURNAL OF HEREDITY* (Vol. 12, p. 351). This is not the place for a discussion of detailed cytological points, and reference will only be made to certain general features, particularly those having a direct bearing on genetics. Miss Carothers has rightly pointed out certain defects in the work in question which are capable of being remedied in a later edition. But she makes a serious blunder in discussing the phenomena of meiosis in plants, with which she evidently has had little experience. She refers to the statement of Sharp that in diakinesis the heterotype chromosomes contrast strikingly with the chromosomes in an ordinary somatic prophase, whether they are secondarily split or not. But she goes on to affirm that "this 'striking contrast,' however, depends wholly upon the fact that the chromosomes are secondarily split, that is that they are tetrads and not dyads." She also states that she "has had enough contact with botanical material to be confident that this statement is true for plants as well as animals."

This statement is particularly unfortunate, because the understanding of

meiosis as it occurs in most plants was retarded for a decade by the search for "tetrads" where they do not exist. It is now well recognized by most plant cytologists that in the majority of plants tetrads do not occur, and that the essential feature of the heterotypic mitosis is the separation of pairs of whole chromosomes. It is easy for such pairs of chromosomes (gemini) to be mistaken for tetrads through a superficial examination, particularly if the observer has the necessity for finding "tetrads" already in mind. As regards animals, there are many instances in which clear tetrads have been observed, but that they are certainly not universal is shown, for example, by the history of the X Y chromosomes in many forms, to take a single example. Some of the more careful recent papers on animal spermatogenesis discard the conception of tetrads and speak of bivalent chromosomes in diakinesis.

The presence of tetrads merely indicates that the paired chromosomes have themselves split before the separation of parts begins. Such a split is necessarily precocious. When this split occurs in the heterotypic anaphase or telophase, as it does in *Oenothera* and *Lactuca* among forms which I have studied critically, then obviously the